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Clinical Evaluation of Diminazene Aceturate and Imidocarb Dipropionate against Bovine Babesiosis and its Prevalence in Cattle of Swat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

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ABSTRACT

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Background: Bovine babesiosis is a common tick-borne disease in cattle that leads to weakness, reduced productivity, and economic losses for farmers. **Aims:** To evaluate the efficacy of Diminazene and Imidocarb against Bovine Babesiosis. **Methodology:** A total of 700 animals from the Tehsils of Babuzai, Matta, Kabal, Barikot, Bahrain, Charbagh, and Khwazakhila had a 3 ml jugular vein sample taken, and the blood was kept in EDTA tubes. Once the blood was stored in ice bags, they were sent to the Veterinary Research and Disease Investigation Center Balogram, Swat, KPK, Pakistan. **Results:** Out of the 700 blood samples from suspected cattle, 48 samples had a positive result for *Babesia bovis*, prevalence of babesiosis was 6.85% in suspected cattle of Swat district. Tehsil Barikot was higher 11%, In age wise the adult was higher 7.85%, sex/gender wise female cattle were higher 8.9% than male which 1.9%, breed wise prevalence mix breed cattle was higher 12.85% compared to local and indigenous cattle, where 2.57% local & 8.57% indigenous cattle. After testing positive for babesiosis, 48 cattle samples were divided into three equal groups, A, B, C and D. Group A cattle received diminazene acetate at a pace of 0.5ml/10kg BW/IM. whereas Group B cattle received imidocarb dipropionate (Imizol) at a rate of 1ml/100 kg BW SC. The animals from group C served as positive control, whereas the animals from group D served as the negative control. On days 0 (premedication) and 3, 7, and 10 (post medication), blood samples were taken from the jugular vein of these cattle, The elimination of *Babesia* in blood smears and the reversal of clinical symptoms were used to assess the effectiveness of the medications. 100% efficiency was seen in the cattle of group B after 10 days of treatment when they were given 2mg/kg body weight with Imazol (Imidocarb Dipropionate). **Conclusion:** It is concluded that bovine babesiosis is present in cattle of Swat district with an overall prevalence of 6.85%, with the highest cases recorded in Barikot 11% and more infections observed in adult cattle 7.85% than calves, gender wise female 8.9% higher than male 1.9%. Furthermore, imidocarb Dipropionate is more potent as compared to Diminazene Aceturate.

INTRODUCTION

Cattle are among the most important species for the global economy, culture, and livestock (Herrero et al., 2013). According to McLeod (2011), there are around 1.5 billion cattle (*Bos taurus* and *B. indicus*) in the globe. In Pakistan, the cumulative dairy cattle population is 51.5 million head, providing an estimated 21,691 to 23,357 million tons of milk, placing Pakistan fourth in the world after China, India and the United States with respect to milk production (Ashraf et al., 2013). A significant obstacle is cattle illnesses, which put dairy farmers at financial danger and The majority of diseases in cattle are caused by ectoparasites and ticks are the most common disease carriers (Vetrivel et al., 2017).

Production losses and several important problems are brought on by parasitic infections in animals worldwide. Multiple diseases that affect the dairy business and, in turn, any country's economy, provide several issues. (Carroll, 2008) Around the world, parasitic infections in animals lead to production losses and several serious problems (Mehmood et al., 2017). The bulk of Pakistan's population resides in rural areas, where animals play a key economic role by producing important animal proteins like milk and meat as well as textiles and skins (Husain et al., 2017).

Even in extremely regulated Environments, exotic cattle breeds are especially vulnerable to tick-borne illnesses According to the current study, 3.92% of the cow herd was afflicted with ticks, Tick infestations in cattle have been documented in prior research to affect 28.2% & 47.9% (Ghafar et al., 2020). The primary objective of animal husbandry is to provide for the demands of the world's population while also ensuring the safety of the products and the wellbeing of the animals. We can notice the ongoing necessity for the enhancement of the present methods of livestock production given the 7% annual increase in consumption of animal products (Ortiz-Gonzalo et al., 2011).

According to (Zeuner 1963), the auroch (*Bos primigenius*) served as the wild ancestor of all domesticated cattle. Now extinct is the aurochs. Two taxa that fully interbreed, (*Bos taurus*) and (*Bos indicus*), are accepted in domestic cattle according to common usage.

Tick-borne illnesses continue to have a large economic impact on the tropical and subtropical animal industries (Berggoetz et al., 2014). Recent increases in populations of ticks and the virulence of the bacteria they carry are caused by global warming, deforestation, and the introduction of new animal species, resulting in significant economic losses (Miranda et al., 2021). Babesia protozoan parasites are known to cause serious infections in humans, animals, and cattle across the world. Babesiosis, theileriosis, anaplasmosis, and trypanosomiasis are the most serious hemoprotozoan illnesses that threaten cattle health and production. Babesia, Theileria, Anaplasma, and Trypanosoma species cause these infections in both animals and humans (Rajput et al., 2005).

Infection with hemoprotozoans has a huge negative impact on human health and productivity as well as that of livestock animals globally, resulting in significant economic losses and restrictions on the global dairy and meat industries. It produces fever, weakness, loss of body condition, cachexia, anemia, a reduction in milk supply, and inadequate draught capacity, though clinical findings differ between species and animals (Juyal, 2005).

Among various tick-borne diseases, babesiosis in cattle is a significant haemoprotozoan disease that causes considerable morbidity and mortality (Sharma et al., 2016). Hemoparasitic infections pose a significant hazard to about 250 million cattle and significantly impede the growth and productivity of livestock in numerous developing nations, Babesiosis presents with symptoms such as high fever and intravascular hemolysis, leading to anemia, icterus, hemoglobinuria, and potentially high mortality rates up to 50%. However, timely and effective treatment and minimal stress can significantly improve outcomes. The infection rate is highest when animals are between 6 and 12 months old. In enzootic areas, calves often get infected around 11 weeks of age, but at this young age, pathological alterations and clinical symptoms are typically minor and transient (Radostits et al., 2000).

Bovine babesiosis, also known as Rut Mootra, is a parasite illness spread by ticks that causes crimson

urine in ruminants. It is caused by haemoprotozoan parasites *Babesia bigemina* and *Babesia bovis*, mostly affecting cattle and buffaloes, which is a global disease (Jaimes et al., 2017). Bovine babesiosis leads to significant economic losses in the livestock and dairy industries due to factors like being wasteful, having an abortion, dying, reduced the cost of control measures and the production of meat and milk (Benavides & Sacco, 2007). Field diagnosis of babesiosis involves observing clinical signs and checking for the presence of ticks on the animal (Kalume et al., 2009). In cases of heavy infestation, a confirmatory diagnosis can be made through microscopy using Giemsa-stained blood smears (Nasir et al., 2000). In Pakistan, babesiosis is the third most significant illness affecting sheep epidemiologically Tick-borne diseases, such as *Babesia* sp., are more prevalent in Pakistan due to the country's ideal climate for vectors (Sajid et al., 2018).

Boophilus microplus, a tick, is to blame for the organism's spread. The susceptible host (cattle) contracts the illness when a tick's salivary gland during a blood meal introduces the sporozoite stage of the *Babesia* species into the blood circulation. When it enters the circulation, it pierces the red blood cell membrane and engages in binary fission, an asexual mode of reproduction, High fever, haemoglobinuria, pale visible mucous membrane, diarrhea, and an abrupt decrease in milk production are the disease's hallmarks (Jyothisree, 2013).

The study population of the districts was examined to evaluate the correlation between the frequency of babesiosis and various hosts and the variables associated with their environment. Factors connected to the host (geography, breed, gender, and age, Imidocarb dipropionate (Imizol, Schering-Plough Animal Health) and diminazene aceturate (Berenil, Intervet, India Pvt. Ltd.) are two babesiacides that are currently prescribed for the treatment of cattle, horses, dogs, and other animals. In addition, humans can utilize quinine, clindamycin, and atovaquone (Mepron, Glaxo Welcome). Due to issues with their toxicity, aftereffects, and the emergence of parasites that are resistant to them, the majority of these babesicidal medications have been shown to be unsuccessful (Bork et al., 2005).

Bovine babesiosis is successfully treated with imidocarb dipropionate and diminazene acceturate, which are the preferred drugs for reducing the economic harm brought on by *Babesia* parasites (Radostitis et al., 2007). Unfortunately, some research has indicated that *Babesia* parasites may eventually evolve Diminazene acceturate resistance (Hwang et al., 2010). Additionally, it has been discovered that Imidocarb dipropionate and Diminazene acceturate have effects that last for up to 21 days and 6 months, respectively, in the edible tissues and milk of sheep and calves (Traynor et al., 2013).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

A total of 700 blood samples (n=100 per tehsil) were collected using random sampling from 7 tehsils of district swat KPK, Pakistan. The study area consisted of district swat (tehsils Babuzai, Matta, Kabal, Barikot, Bahrain charbagh & khwazakheila) in the province of KPK, Pakistan. District swat has an area of 5337km² and a total population of 2308624, including urban population of 695821 and rural population of 16128030 According to the national 2017 census (Figure 1).

vacutainer tubes containing EDTA. Once the blood was stored in ice bags, they were sent to the Veterinary Research and Disease Investigation Center in Balogram, Swat, KPK, Parasitology Laboratory. After air drying and methanol fixation for two to three minutes, the sample creates a tiny film of blood. Staining was done with 5% Giemsa stain. At least 50 fields were searched per slide while examining the smears under a compound microscope set to 100x magnification.

Preparation of thin smear

The glass slide was cleaned before preparing the tiny smear. A little drop of blood was placed into one end of the clean, dry slide. To make a tongue-shaped smear, a spreader slide inclined at 45 degrees was pushed horizontally from one end to the other. The produced smear was promptly air-dried before being fixed in methanol for around 3-5 minutes.

Factors Associated with Bovine Babesiosis

The study population of the districts was examined to evaluate the correlation between the frequency of babesiosis and various hosts and the variables associated with their environment. The location, age, sex, & breed, taken into consideration to find a correlation occurrence of disease. Babesiosis has been linked to several factors, including age, sex, breed, and season.

Microscopic examination

Thin blood smears were prepared, fixed for five minutes in methanol, and then stained for ten minutes with Giemsa stain. The blood samples were thinly smeared onto the freshly labeled glass slides., which will subsequently be examined under a 100x objective magnification for Babesia species. Absolute methyl alcohol was used to fix the dried blood smears for a duration of one minute. To detect the presence of *B. bovis*, glass slides containing Giemsa stain, which are readily accessible commercially, were diluted four times and applied to thin blood smears. The samples were then viewed under an oil immersion microscope with an objective of 100X.

The conventional model of babesiosis examination is a direct examination under a microscope. It is used to identify the agent in the infected host. This is accomplished by examining thick and thin films and then staining them with Giemsa or Romanowsky stain. Thick films can detect parasites as few as one parasite out of 106 RBCs (Kahn 2005). Microscopic examination is still the most cost-effective and time-efficient technique for identifying Babesia parasites (Hamoda et al. 2014). Giemsa-stained thin blood smears are the traditional and gold standard for identification and serve as an ideal method for species differentiation. It is adequate for detecting acute infections but has lower effects in cases of low parasitemia in carriers (Criado-Fornelio et al., 2009; Bal et al., 2016; Masih et al., 2021).

Prevalence Assessment of Babesiosis

The following formula was used to compute the prevalence of positive parasite in cattle, which was recorded area-wise, age-wise, & gender-wise, Giemsa-stained blood smears were examined under a microscope to check for the presence of Babesia parasites. Rate of prevalence the following formula was utilized to get the prevalence rate. Number of positive samples / Number of total samples x 100 equals P. Rate.

Prevalence formula

$$P \% = \frac{\text{No positive sample}}{\text{No of total sample}} \times 100$$

Chemotherapy

After testing positive for babesiosis, 48 positive cattle were divided into three equal groups, A, B, and C. In the investigation, ten more healthy cattle made up Group D. Diminazene Aceturate was given to Group

A's cattle at a rate of 0.5 ml/10 kg BW 1M. Imidocarb dipropionate was administered to Group B's cattle at a rate of 1ml/100 kg BW SC. The animals from group C served as positive control, whereas the animals from group D served as the negative control. Blood samples were obtained from the cattle's jugular vein on days 0 (premedication) and 3, 7, and 10 (post medication). Giemsa dye was used to stain these blood samples, which were then smeared thin and examined under a microscope. The elimination Clinical reversal of babesia in blood smears symptoms was used to assess the effectiveness of the medications.

STATISTICAL DESIGN

The data were analyzed by statistix (version 8.1) Chi-square test was used to check the level of significance.

RESULTS

Overall prevalence of babesiosis in cattle of district swat

The prevalence of babesiosis in suspected cattle in the SWAT district was ascertained. Out of the 700 blood samples from suspected cattle, 48 samples had a positive result for *Babesia bovis* the prevalence is 6.85% of the sample was positive (table 1).

Table 1. Overall Prevalence of Babesiosis in suspected cattle of District Swat KPK

Total samples	positive samples	Percentage of positive samples
700	48	6.85%

Factors Associated with Bovine Babesiosis

The study population of the districts was examined to evaluate the correlation between the frequency of babesiosis and various hosts and the variables associated with their environment. Factors connected to the host (geography, breed, gender, and age) The study population of the districts was examined to evaluate the correlation between the frequency of babesiosis and various hosts and the variables associated with their environment. The location, age, sex & breed taken into consideration find a correlation occurrence of babesiosis.

Babesiosis has been linked to several factors, including area, age, sex, breed, and season.

Area or tehsil wise prevalence of babesiosis. In cattle of Swat district

Seven hundred blood samples were taken from various locations within the district SWAT; of them, forty-eight samples were positive for *Babesia* spp. Babesiosis prevalence in SWAT is 6.85% for infected cattle in the districts of Barikot (11% positive), which has the highest incidence among all the districts (Babuzai, Matta, Kabal, Barikot, Bahrain, Charbagh, & Khwazakhila) (Table 2).

Table 2. Area or Tehsil wise Prevalence of Babesiosis in Cattle of Swat District

Tehsils Factor area	Samples examine	Positive samples	Prevalence%	Chi square	P-Value
Babuzai	100	8	8%	30.34	0.0069
Matta	100	4	4%		
Kabal	100	9	9%		

Barikot	100	11	11%	30.34	0.0069
Bahrain	100	1	1%		
Charbagh	100	7	7%		
Khwazakheila	100	8	8%		
Total	700	48	6.85%		

Age wise prevalence of babesiosis in cattle of district swat

700 From district swat, blood samples from animals were obtained. The slides from the blood smear were inspected under a microscope. 48 blood samples out of 700 were positive for Babesia species. *B. bovis* was detected in 48 samples in all. out of 35 calves 2 sample positive, in 245 heifer sample 13 are positive sample and in adults 420 sample 33 were positive. the highest in adults 7.8% and the lowest calves just 2 positive samples (Table 3).

Table 3. Age wise Prevalence of Babesiosis in Cattle of Swat District

Age of Cattle	Total examine samples	Positive samples	Prevalence%	Chi square	P-Value
Calves	35	2	5.71%	3.92	0.688
Heifer	245	13	5.30%		
Adults	420	33	7.85%		
Total	700	48	6.85%	3.92	0.688

Sex wise prevalence of babesiosis

4 of the 210 male cows and calves tested positive for babesiosis, compared to 44 of the 490 female cows and calves who tested positive. Four of the 210 blood samples from male cattle that were examined turned out to be *B. bovis*-positive, while 44 of the 490 blood samples from female cattle were discovered to be *B. bovis*-positive (Table 4).

Table 4. Sex or Gender wise Prevalence of Babesiosis in cattle of Swat District

Sex/ gender	Examine samples	Positive samples	Prevalence%	Chi square	P-Value
Male	210	4	1.9%	10.35	0.349
Female	490	44	8.97%		
Total	700	48	6.85%	10.35	0.349

Breed wise Prevalence of Babesiosis

Out of 350 local breed samples were collected 9 sample were positive, 210 mix breed animals' sample were collected 27 were positive & 140 indigenous breed sample were collected and just 12 sample were positive (Table 5)

Table 5. Breed wise Prevalence of Babesiosis

Breeds	Examine samples	Positive samples	Prevalence%	Chi square	P-Value
local	350	9	2.57%	24.39	0.0004
Mix	210	27	12.85%		
Indigenous	140	12	8.57%		
Total	700	48	6.85%	24.39	0.0004

Table 6. Efficacy of Imidocarb Dipropionate & Diminazene Aceturate against Babesiosis in Cattle of Swat District

Group n=10	Medicine/ drugs	Drug efficacy (%) during the days		
		3	7	10
a	Diminazene Aceturate	40	50	90
b	Imidocarb Dipropionate	70	90	100
c	Positive control			
d	Negative Control			

Figure 2. Efficacy of Imidocarb Dipropionate & Diminazene Aceturate against Babesiosis in cattle of Swat District

Chemotherapy

Three equal groups of the 48 animals with positive results were formed. A, B, and C, when their results were confirmed. Group D consisted of ten more healthy cattle from the inquiry. The animals in Group A administered diminazene aceturate at a rate of 0.5ml/10 kg BW 1M. The cattle in group B imidocarb dipropionate at a rate of 1ml/100 kg BW SC. Group C's animals functioned as the positive control, while group D's animals acted as negative control. Three, seven, and ten days after the cattle were given medicine, and day 0 was when blood samples were taken from their jugular vein. These blood samples were stained with Giemsa dye, smeared thin, and viewed under a microscope. The effectiveness of the drugs was evaluated by looking for the removal of Babesia in serum smears and the clinical symptoms' reversal. The cattle in group A demonstrated 90% efficacy after 10 days of therapy when given 3 mg/kg body weight with Fa-try-banil (diminazene aceturate) (Table 6 and Figure 2). Diminazene aceturate is most frequently utilized in practice dose of 3 to 5 mg/kg body weight. After receiving imizol (imidocarb dipropionate) 2mg/kg body weight medication, animals in Group B showed 70% efficacy on Day 3, 90% on Day 7, and 100% on Day 10.

DISCUSSION

Parasitic infections such as babesiosis have a huge influence on the worldwide cattle sector, resulting in a complex web of implications that go beyond immediate animal health problems. These consequences have an impact on trade, economies, and even human health, posing threats to agricultural production and economic stability (Omeragic et al., 2022; Chakraborty et al., 2023). Bovine babesiosis is a serious illness that has a negative impact on cow productivity and reproduction. The most often reported parasites in cattle are *B. bovis* and *B. bigemina* (Elsify et al., 2015, Ibrahim et al., 2013). In the United Kingdom, bovine babesiosis, often known as red water fever, is a tick-borne sickness that occurs during the spring, summer, and fall. The condition is distinguished by a temperature & hemolysis within the vessels, which leads anemia, Itches, hemoglobinuria & death.

In Pakistan, babesiosis affects cattle and buffaloes at rates ranging from 5.5% to 42.8%. According to research conducted in Swat, 6.85% of 700 blood samples from suspected cattle proved positive for *Babesia bovis*. These results are consistent with those Nazir (2002) found a 7% incidence of *Babesia bovis* in bovine cattle in the Malakand Agency, NWFP, Pakistan reported a prevalence ranging from 7.6% to 18.2% in Argentina. Aulakh (2003) found a prevalence of 5.94% in India, which is like the findings of this study. Differences in prevalence rates might be attributed to differing meteorological conditions. The current study's findings contrast from those of the prevalence rates ranged from 70% to 100%, according to Chandrawathani et al. (1994) and Bell et al. (2004) investigations. The use of extremely sensitive diagnostic techniques like PCR, ELISA, and CFT may be the cause of this discrepancy.

Similarly, study conducted in China revealed 7.24% prevalence rate of Babesia infection in Philippines 11.49% (Herrera et al., 2017). The study of animal population of all the districts was examined to evaluate the correlation between the frequency of babesiosis & various hosts & the variables associated with their environment. The location, age, sex, breed, & seasons of the year were taken into consideration to find a correlation with the occurrence of babesiosis. Babesiosis has been linked to several factors, including age, sex, breed, and season.

Babesiosis is prevalent in Tehsil Barikot, with an incidence of 11%. This high prevalence might be attributed to ticks' preference for hot and moist environments that promote their development. Furthermore, the frequency in adult cattle was greater, at 7.85%. The study also looked at the frequency of *B. bovis* based on the age of the cattle, finding that the rate of babesiosis reduced with age. Female cattle had the greatest B.

bovis prevalence (8.97%), whereas male cattle had a lower frequency (1.9%). The increased occurrence in females might be attributable to the widespread use of infected needles for administering medications for milk letdown or illness treatment. This study's findings differed from Ahmad et al. (2014) but were similar with Ayaz et al. (2013). Finally, mixed breed cattle had a greater rate of babesiosis (12.85%) than local (2.57%) or indigenous cattle (8.57%).

Although this figure does not fully represent the number of animals at risk for the disease, the majority of the 1.2 billion cattle worldwide are exposed to babesiosis (McCosker, 1981) Imidocarb dipropionate & diminazene aceturate are believed to be efficacious therapies for infections caused by *Babesia bovis*. Trypanocide diminazene, also known as diminazene aceturate, is widely used to treat babesiosis in cattle. Imidocarb dipropionate is another drug that's commonly used to treat babesiosis in cattle. The choice between imidocarb dipropionate and diminazene aceturate for treating babesiosis may be impacted by regional veterinary guidelines, medication accessibility, and distinctive characteristics of the infection. Nevertheless, a variety of factors, such as the parasite strain, the animal's condition, the dosage, and the timing of the therapy, might affect how effective 48 sample positive are & divided by three groups A, B, and C. Group D consisted of 10 additional healthy cattle that were added to the trial. While the cattle in group B received imidocarb dipropionate at 1ml/100kg BW SC, the cattle in group A received diminazene aceturate at 0.5 ml/10 kg BW IM. Group D's animals were kept as the negative control, and group C's animals as the positive control. The jugular vein of these calves was used to draw blood samples on days 0 (premedication) and 3, 7, & 10 (post medication). These blood samples were stained with Giemsa dye, made into a thin smear, and inspected under a microscope.

Cattle team A handled Fa-try-banil (diminazene aceturate) at a dose of 3 mg/kg bw and demonstrated ninety percent (90%) effectiveness by the 10th day (Table 6). These findings are consistent with Kuttler (1980), who said that diminazene aceturate at 3-5 mg/kg body weight is widely utilized. The are also consistent with Aulakh (2003), who utilized quinapyramine sulfate at 3 to5 mg/kg BW subcutaneously, buparvaquone at 1cc/20kilogram bw intramuscularly, & diminazene aceturate at 1.6 gm/100kg BW intramuscularly to treat trypanosomiasis, India is home to theileriosis and babesiosis. Group B animals received treated with imidocarb dipropionate, or Imizol. at a dose of 2 mg/kg and demonstrated 70% effectiveness on day three (3), 90% on day seven (7), and 100% on day (10). These findings are congruent with Kuttler (1980) and Karimov and Gafurov (1984), who effectively treated bovine babesia with imidocarb dipropionate dose 2 mg/kg BW. Diminazene aceturate and imidocarb dipropionate have long been the primary treatments for animal babesiosis. However, they have downsides, such as longer tissue removal times and restricted availability in some regions.

Yamasaki et al. (2017) found that imidocarb dipropionate and diminazene aceturate are efficient treatments for bovine babesiosis and reduce economic loss caused by *Babesia* parasites (Radostitis et al., 2007). While various effective babesiacides have been documented in the literature, only a handful are accessible business-wise. The most often used ones now are imidocarb dipropionate (imidocarb) and diminazene aceturate. 1.2 mg/kg of imidocarb subcutaneously provides protection against *B. bovis* for four weeks and against *B. bigemina* for at least two months (Taylor & McHardy, 1979). Currently, imidocarb dipropionate and diminazene aceturate are used to treat cattle, horses, dogs, and other animals.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded from the current study that *Babesia bovis* was found in 48 samples (6.85%) of the 700 suspected cattle in the Swat area, with Barikot having the highest frequency (11%). Calves had the lowest rate of infection (2/35), while adults had the greatest rate (33/420; 7.8%). Additionally, 13/245 heifers, 44/490 females, and 9/350 local, 27/210 crossbred, and 12/140 indigenous cattle tested positive. The 48 positive animals were split into groups to test diminazene aceturate (5 ml/10 kg IM) and imidocarb dipropionate (1 ml/100 kg SC). The results showed improvement in signs and a decrease in *Babesia* in blood smears,

suggesting that these medications, along with effective tick control, vaccinations, and medications, are crucial for managing babesiosis.

Authors' Contribution

AR is researcher and author of manuscript. JK supervised study conducted. AHM guided to conduct research in laboratory. JK, MS, TA, MA helped in formal analysis. SN, IL, MA, IU BK contributed to manuscript writing, reviews, and editing.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The original data of study is available.

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